

Analysis on the Impact of Company Employer Branding with the Desire of Generation Z in Choosing Their Workplace: A Case Study of PT BRI

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ABSTRACT: Generation Z's entry into the workforce has shifted perspectives on work. They have clear job expectations and are more demanding, seeking fulfillment, purpose, and a better quality of life. Employers who prioritize these needs will attract and retain Generation Z, shaping the future of work. They are technologically adept, socially aware, and engaged in global issues. Despite uncertain times due to the pandemic, rapid technological growth, and potential economic recessions, Gen Z enters the workforce with clear job expectations. The primary research objective is to develop employer branding strategies that align with the values and expectations of Gen Z. The methodology used in this research is Interactive Model Analysis to know what the important factor for Gen Z is according to Employer Attractiveness Scale (EmpAt). Primary data are acquired by doing an in-depth interview with several employees of PT BRI and also from external that is Gen Z who are currently working in a startup. This research revealed that from 5 dimensions of EmpAt, the most important one to explore is Safety Values because it is one of the benefits of working in a BUMN company.

KEYWORDS: BUMN, Employer Branding, Employer Attractiveness, Generation Z, Startup.

1. INTRODUCTION

Gen Z, born between the mid-1990s and mid-2010s, is entering the workforce during uncertain times marked by the COVID-19 pandemic, technological advancements, and potential economic recession. They have unique expectations and demands in the workplace. They prioritize quality of life, personal fulfillment, and a sense of purpose. Gen Z's preferences, including their emphasis on leadership, CSR, social media, and communication, will shape the future of work. Job seekers are more selective, considering factors like company culture, work-life balance, and career development. Employer branding is crucial to attract and retain top talent. Gen Z values factors such as pay, career advancement, employee benefits, enjoyment at work, diversity, equity, inclusion, and sustainability in their job choices. (Handshake, 2022).

A survey conducted by an HR consulting firm to find interest and preferences of Gen Z, the survey focuses on 4 points: Leadership, CSR, social media, and Communication. (Randstad, 2015).

The behavior of job seekers has changed, with candidates being more selective in their job search and placing a greater emphasis on factors such as company culture, work-life balance, and career development opportunities. In order to attract and keep top talent, companies had to modify their recruitment techniques and place a greater emphasis on developing their employer branding. Employer branding can also be used as a strategy to retain the current employees from competitors by creating a positive perception of the company as an employer.

Handshake conducted a survey for students and recent graduates on factors that would make them apply to a workplace and can make them stay. The result of the survey indicates that there are 6 main factors that Gen Z consider as important for their next job, the 6 factors are: pay or compensation, ability to advance career, employee benefits, having fun at the job, commitment to diversity, equity, inclusion, and belonging (DEIB), and commitment to sustainability. (Handshake, 2022).

BUSINESS ISSUE

From the interview result with The HR of Directorate of Digital, Technology and Information (DTI) at PT Bank Rakyat Indonesia (BRI), the challenges faced by the company is that many top talents of the current generation (Gen Z) prefer to start their career at startup, e-commerce or private company before going to a company like BUMN. So, they want to improve their employer branding to be able to secure top talents and compete with those companies. This aligns with their human resources strategy in which they

want to become the most valuable banking group in Southeast Asia and in order to achieve it one of the supporting factors is by recruiting the best talent available. The year-on-year comparison of employee numbers in BRI reveals a notable decrease from 2021 to 2022. This decline in the total workforce can be attributed to various factors, with a significant portion being attributed to a decrease in employees from the Generation Z age range.

Gen Z, known as the "Hustle Generation", is characterized by their entrepreneurial mindset and ambition. They are proactive in seeking opportunities and leveraging technology for multiple income streams. Despite the pandemic, there is a global rise in entrepreneurship and startup intentions, driven by necessity, opportunity, and individual aspirations. This trend showcases the resilience and adaptability of entrepreneurs and emphasizes the role of supportive ecosystems and government policies in fostering entrepreneurial growth. Increased entrepreneurship offers potential for economic recovery and innovation.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Generation Z

Generation Z, born between 1995 and 2012, is a digitally influenced and diverse generation. They embrace new ideas, value experiences, and exhibit a higher inclination towards entrepreneurship. Growing up after the Great Recession and in the era of social media, they are globally connected and have been shaped by technology. (Twenge, 2017)

Employer Branding

Employer branding is the perception of an organization by its employees and stakeholders. It involves promoting the company's unique qualities to create an appealing workplace and align employees with its vision. It helps attract and retain top talent, providing a competitive advantage. (Michington and Estis, 2009)

Organizational Attractiveness

In the competitive healthcare industry, organizations should aim to be attractive employers by creating a desirable workplace. Factors such as reputation, culture, benefits, and advancement opportunities contribute to organizational attractiveness. By highlighting their strengths, employers can influence career choices and attract talented individuals. (Sivertzen, Nilsen and Olafsen, 2013)

Generation Z Important Job Factors

The survey findings by Handshake in 2022 reveal that Gen Z identifies 6 primary factors as significant for their future employment prospects. These 6 factors include:

1. Compensation that affords work-life balance

Gen Z considers factors like cost of living, remote work options, industry hubs, work-life benefits, affordable living, student debt, and access to pay data when choosing jobs. Transparent compensation information helps shape their expectations.

2. Clarity into career paths and internal mobility opportunities

Gen Z values ownership, exclusive projects, upskilling opportunities, mentorship, support, and frequent feedback for skill development. HR leaders prioritize skill building for Gen Z's early career experiences.

3. A modernized approach to benefits with an emphasis on flexibility and mental health

Early career job seekers prioritize work-life balance, including financial, physical, and mental health benefits. Flexibility in work schedules, and remote work options. Gen Z seeks control over their schedules with preferences for unlimited or flexible paid time off and remote work.

4. Community, culture, and collaboration even in remote settings

Early career talent values collaboration, networking, and socializing. They rely on crowd-sourced reviews to assess job prospects. Gen Z seeks meaningful work, community building, cultural experiences, and networking opportunities to foster team integration. They appreciate engaging team bonding activities and projects aligned with their career goals.

5. Committing publicly to diversity, equity, inclusion, and belonging (DEIB)

Gen Z expects social justice commitment from employers and brands. They observe responses to social issues and layoffs. Consistent DEIB efforts are essential for retaining Gen Z. They use open forums and digital platforms to voice opinions and hold brands accountable.

6. Accountability on the environment, sustainability, and social responsibility

Gen Z seeks meaningful work aligned with their values and a broader mission. They prioritize making an impact over money and are passionate about social and environmental issues. They encourage corporations to have strong social responsibility programs.

Employer Attractiveness Measurement Scale (EmpAt)

An employer attractiveness scale is a tool that measures how appealing an employer is to potential employees based on factors like reputation, work environment, compensation, career growth, work-life balance, and organizational culture. It helps individuals rate and rank employers for their attractiveness. (Berthon, 2005). There are 5 dimensions of employer attractiveness scale:

1. Social Value (SOC)

This dimension relates to the level of attraction an individual feels towards an employer based on a positive work environment, strong working relationships, and a team-oriented atmosphere. Social value refers to the appeal of a business that offers a fun, happy work environment, good working relationships, and positive team dynamics.

2. Development Value (DEV)

This dimension pertains to the attractiveness an individual feels towards an employer based on factors such as recognition, professional engagement, and opportunities for future growth. Developmental values, including growth opportunities and confidence-building experiences, motivate employees to excel. Social exchange theory suggests that the exchange between employers and employees includes material and social benefits.

3. Application Value (APP)

This dimension relates to the attraction individuals feel towards employers that provide opportunities to apply their knowledge and skills in a humanistic and customer-oriented work environment.

4. Safety Value (SAF)

This dimension reflects the attraction individuals have towards employers that prioritize safety and security at work. Ethical leadership style and employee awareness contribute to increased engagement within the organization.

5. Economic Value (ECO)

This dimension represents the attraction individuals have towards companies that offer competitive compensation, benefits, and bonus packages in terms of average wages.

From those 5 values an interview questions were made.

Table 1. Interview Questions

No.	Dimensions	Source
I	Social value (SOC): 6 items	
1	<i>Having a good relationship with your colleagues.</i>	Berthon et al. (2005)
2	<i>Supportive and encouraging colleagues.</i>	Berthon et al. (2005)
3	<i>Having a good relationship with your superiors.</i>	Berthon et al. (2005)
4	<i>Happy work environment.</i>	Berthon et al. (2005)
5	<i>A fun working environment.</i>	Berthon et al. (2005)
II	Development value (DEV): 6 items	
1	<i>Feeling good about yourself as a result of working for a particular organization.</i>	Berthon et al. (2005)
2	<i>Feeling more self-confident as a result of working for a particular organization.</i>	Berthon et al. (2005)

3	<i>A springboard for future employment.</i>	Berthon et al. (2005)
4	<i>Gaining career-enhancing experience.</i>	Berthon et al. (2005)
III	Application value (APP): 4 items	
1	<i>Opportunity to teach others what you have learned.</i>	Berthon et al. (2005)
2	<i>Opportunity to apply what was learned at a tertiary institution.</i>	Berthon et al. (2005)
3	<i>Acceptance and belonging.</i>	Berthon et al. (2005)
IV	Safety value (SAF): 3 items	
1	<i>Job security within the organization.</i>	Berthon et al. (2005)
2	<i>The organization I work with is always safe in the work environment (without pressure, sexual harassment, etc.).</i>	Qualitative research
V	Economic value (ECO): 3 items	
1	<i>An above-average basic salary.</i>	Berthon et al. (2005)
2	<i>An attractive overall compensation package.</i>	Berthon et al. (2005)
	Total: 16 items	

Conceptual Framework

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

The five values contributing to employer attractiveness vary in importance for individuals. The dimensions of attractiveness depend on employees' needs and expectations. For instance, those seeking a high-paying job prioritize economic value over social value. Selected values serve as the basis for creating the most suitable employer attractiveness factor that contributes to a company's employer branding.

3. METHODOLOGY

Data for this research will be collected through primary sources using in-depth interviews and secondary sources through literature study. In-depth interviews involve unstructured, face-to-face conversations to explore participants' motivations, beliefs, attitudes, and emotions on a specific topic. The focus is on open-ended dialogue and interpreting participant discourse for meaningful insights, rather than seeking factual information.

Interviewee criteria were established in advance to align with the research objectives and achieve optimal outcomes. The criteria include selecting interviewees from Gen Z (below the age of 27) and representing diverse genders, divisions, and lengths of work or positions within the company. Additional respondents from outside the company, working in startups, were also included. The interview questions were constructed using the Employer Attractiveness Scale as a benchmark.

The most suitable data analysis method for the collected data is the Interactive Analysis Model, which consists of four parts: data collection, data condensation (coding), data display, and conclusion. Qualitative data will be processed using manual coding, where meaningful segments are identified and labeled. Prior steps include establishing research questions and design, conducting a literature review, and systematically collecting data. The interview results will be transcribed, coded, and analyzed by the researcher.

Figure 2. Research Methodology

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

To analyze the interview results of BRI Employees and external employees is by using framework by Berthon that consists of 5 Value; Social, Development, Application, Safety, and Economic.

Table 2. Demographic Information of the Internal Employee of BRI Interviewees

No	Name	Sex	Age	Length of work	Last Education
1	I1	Female	23	10 months	S1 Sistem Informasi
2	I2	Male	24	2 years	S1 Teknik Elektro
3	I3	Female	25	4 years	S1 Teknik Informatika
4	I4	Male	26	1,5 years	S1 IT
5	I5	Female	26	2 years	S1 Teknik Elektro
6	I6	Male	25	2 years	S1 Teknik Penerbangan

Table 3. Demographic Information from External Employee Interviewees

No	Name	Sex	Age	Length of work	Last Education	Position/Company
1	O1	Male	22	1 year	S1 Teknik Industri	Software Engineer in logistic company
2	O2	Male	25	6 months	S1 Teknik Geologi	Sales and marketing in distribution company
3	O3	Male	23	2 years	S1 Teknik Informatika	Software Engineer in service company
4	O4	Female	24	3 months	S1 Psikologi	UX researcher in foreign tech company
5	O5	Female	24	6 months	S1 Arsitektur	Managing director in creative agency
6	O6	Male	25	2 years	S1 Teknik Geologi	Warehouse project at ecommerce

Social Value (SOC)

Interviews showed positive relationships, support, open communication, collaboration at BRI. One interviewee mentioned slower pace due to being state-owned. Overall, BRI fosters good relationships and support. And the interview results from startup employee reveal almost the same answer with all of them having a good relationship with their coworkers with some of them having supportive work environment and there are some of them who have a competitive and challenging work environment.

Development Value (DEV)

Interviews indicate that working at BRI boosts confidence and promotes career growth. State-owned status and assessments/certifications enhance confidence. Structured progression and learning opportunities are valued. Overall, BRI positively impacts confidence and careers. Meanwhile for the startup employees interviews reveal increased confidence through skill acquisition. Career advancement opportunities mentioned, but some seek clearer progression paths.

Application Value (APP)

The interviews show that some individuals in the IT department at BRI have had opportunities to teach and share knowledge. This has helped them feel connected to the organization. However, experiences vary, with some not having the chance to teach and feeling less connected as a result. Overall, teaching opportunities influence their sense of belonging at BRI. And the interview results with startup employees suggest that interviewees had teaching opportunities, felt valued due to organizational culture and values.

Safety Value (SAF)

Interviews reveal a sense of job security and safe working environment at BRI, attributed to being a state-owned enterprise. Quite difference from the interview of BRI employees, the interview results with startup employees suggest that most of them doesn't feel secure with their job security due to uncertainty in the company stability although there are believe that they could still stay there for the next few years. The work environment is considered as safe for all interviewee.

Economic Value (ECO)

Interviews show mixed views on compensation at BRI, with some finding it satisfactory while others have concerns about salary growth and negotiation. While all the startup employees are satisfied with the current compensation that they received

Employer Attractiveness

Based on the interview results, BRI demonstrates strong employer attractiveness for Generation Z. The organization offers a supportive work environment, positive relationships among colleagues, job security, and a safe working environment. Opportunities for confidence building, career growth, and knowledge sharing contribute to employees' sense of belonging. BRI's independent IT infrastructure and benefits are appealing, although opinions on compensation vary. The diverse motivations and expectations reflect BRI's appeal as an employer, providing professional development, stability, and the chance to create value through work. Overall, the interviews indicate that BRI is an attractive employer.

From the interview of Gen Z who are currently working in startup in general most of them are satisfied in Social, Development, Application, and Economic Values. However, despite their overall satisfaction, there is a notable concern among Gen Z employees in startups regarding the safety value of their jobs. Many view their positions as less secure and stable in the long term compared to established companies.

Business Solution

Improve Social Media Employer Branding

Social media has become crucial for companies to enhance their employer branding, especially with the rise of Generation Z. Platforms like Instagram and TikTok provide a unique opportunity to engage with this tech-savvy generation. Over half of Generation Z individuals spend at least four hours per day on social media, with 38% spending even more time. Gen Z uses social media for online shopping, video consumption, and following influencers. BRI has effectively utilized social media for employer branding on their Instagram account, but there is room to expand the content to include the professional aspects of working at BRI. 72% of job seekers use social media to research companies before applying. To attract Gen Z, BRI can create engaging content on TikTok showcasing the work environment and employee experiences, following the success of campaigns like Shopee's.

Provide Free Educational or Skill Class

BRI can boost awareness of BRI's commitment to employee development and attract talent by offering free skill classes taught by its own employees. BRI can collaborate with experienced online learning platforms to conduct the classes.

5. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

Conclusion

Several factors influence employer branding, including Social Value, Development Value, Application Value, Safety Value, and Economic Value. The interviews with BRI employees indicate overall satisfaction across all dimensions. However, external respondents express concerns about the safety value, as job security in startups is seen as less guaranteed in the long term. Career growth is a priority for respondents in their current age, but they consider joining BUMN in the future due to the perceived job security.

There are 2 proposed solutions to develop employer branding strategies that align with the values and expectations of Gen Z, the first one is by improving social media employer branding to captivate Gen Z's attention and effectively demonstrate the BRI work environment, it is essential to create captivating and relatable content and the second one is by providing free educational or skill classes, this could raise awareness about the continuous growth opportunities available at BRI, it's crucial to highlight that the company encourages and supports employee skill enhancement. BRI facilitates this by offering access to courses and financing for desired skill classes.

RECOMMENDATION

Recommendation for company

BRI can implement the 2 proposed solution that was already explained in the previous chapter in less than 1 year if both solutions run simultaneously. The solutions are; improving employer branding through social media and provide free educational/skill classes alongside it.

Recommendation for future research

Future researcher can carry out a different method to gain the data like using questionnaire so it can reach more audience. The demographic for respondents could also be determined beforehand by selecting respondents from different economical background

so the responds could be more varied. When conducting the research make sure that the data needed is obtainable.

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